

Bioactive Marine Alkaloids

D. S. BHAKUNI

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

Manuscript received 29 September 1993

The chemistry and biology of bioactive marine alkaloids isolated during the last ten years have been reviewed. Syntheses of bioactive marine indole alkaloids, aplysinopsins, bromoaplysinopsins, their relative and their biological activities are reported.

Marine organisms during the last twentyfive years have yielded a variety of bioactive secondary metabolites¹⁻⁷. Of these the alkaloids are of considerable interest because of the novelty in structures and biological activities. Marine alkaloids have been isolated both from marine plants and animals. The largest number of bioactive alkaloids with novel structure have come particularly from marine sponges and tunicates. Some of the alkaloids from marine microorganisms are extremely toxic. Whereas, the alkaloids from marine invertebrates particularly from marine sponge and tunicate exhibit antifungal, antimicrobial, anticancer, immunomodulator and other types of pharmacological activities.

Bacterial marine alkaloids

A highly brominated pyrrole derivative (1) is the first alkaloid isolated from a bacterial source⁸. Although this bacterium was isolated from surface of the caribbean seagrass *Thalassia*, it was found to belong to a well known group of gram-negative seawater bacterium.

The alkaloid was composed of more than 70% bromine by weight and was fully characterised by X-ray crystallographic method⁹. It showed impressive *in vitro* antibiotic properties against

gram-positive bacteria. However, it was found inactive *in vivo*. It also exhibited antitumor properties. A synthesis of the alkaloid (1) is reported¹⁰.

2

Several years later a tetrabromopyrrole (2) along with other metabolites were isolated from the purple-coloured bacterium of the genus *Alteromonas*¹¹. Compound 2 showed moderate antimicrobial activity *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Candida albicans*. 6-Bromoindolecarboxaldehyde (3), its debrominated analogues and a mixture of 4 and 5 exhibiting antibiotic properties

3

4, R = n - C₇H₁₃

5, R = n - C₅H₁₁

were isolated from the bacterium from a La Jolla, CA, tide pool seawater sample¹². A structurally-novel alkaloid, altermicidin (**6**) is produced by a marine strain of *Streptomyces sioyaensis*^{13,14}. Altermicidin (**6**) showed potent antitumor activity *in vitro* against L 1210 murine leukemia and IMC carcinoma cell lines with IC₅₀ value of 0.84 and 0.82 µg/ml respectively.

It showed weak antibacterial activity, but was relatively toxic in mice (LD₅₀ 0.3 mg/kg, i.v.), probably limiting its chemotherapeutic uses. Altermicidin is an exceptionally novel sulphur and nitrogen-containing alkaloid. Biosynthesis of altermicidin has not been defined. It has been suggested that altermicidin (**6**) having a monoterpene

6

carbon skeleton may be produced via the mevalonate pathway¹⁵.

Several highly toxic nitrogen containing metabolites have been isolated from marine symbiotic bacteria¹⁵. Neosurugatoxin first found along with prosurugatoxin in the edible Japanese mollusc *Bahylonia japonica*¹⁶ was later traced to a gram-positive bacterium from the digestive gland of the animal¹⁷. Nitrogen-containing potent marine neurotoxin, tetrodotoxin (**7**) until recently was

7

thought to be produced by pufferfish of the family tetraodontidae. In Japan, the pufferfish, known as 'Fugu' are considered a delicacy and

great care is taken in preparing and consuming the flesh of the toxic fish. Despite great care a few deaths are reported each year from pufferfish intoxication¹⁵. Tetrodotoxin (**7**) has now been isolated from crabs, an octopus, a goby, mollusc, flatworm and even a terrestrial amphibian, all suggesting a microbial source. It has now been conclusively proved that tetrodotoxin (**7**) is produced by numerous unicellular marine bacteria¹⁸⁻²⁰.

It is very unusual to find the same molecule being produced so widely and by several bacteria genera. It is believed that the production of tetrodotoxin (**7**) is probably linked to a plasmid which can be transferred within marine environments¹⁵. Saxitoxin (**8**), the causative toxin involved

8

in 'paralytic shellfish poisoning' (PSP) was known to be a metabolite of marine dinoflagellate of the genus *Alexandrium*. Recently, kodama and coworkers²¹ have firmly proved that a marine bacterium *Moraxella* sp is the true source of saxitoxin.

Three quinazoline derivatives, fumiquinazolines A (**9**), B (**10**) and C (**11**) exhibiting moderate cytotoxic activity against the cultured P 388

9, R' = Me, R'' = H
10, R' = H; R'' = Me

lymphocytic leukemia cells, have been isolated from *Aspergillus fumigatus*²² which existed in the gastrointestinal tract of the saltwater fish *Pseudolabrus japonicus*.

11

Several tetra- and pentacyclic aromatic alkaloids having a pyrido[4,3,2-*mn*]acridine skeleton or benzo-3,6-diazaphenanthroline skeleton have been isolated from sponges and sea anemones²³. These alkaloids, although obtained from diverse sources, are chemically closely related suggesting thus that they might originate from symbiotic microorganisms. Wakayin (**12**), a pyrroloiminoquinone

12

alkaloid exhibiting cytotoxic, antimicrobial, and DNA damaging activities, has been isolated from a tunicate *Clavelina* sp²⁴. The structure of wakayin is closely related to that of discorhabodin C and prianosin A isolated from marine sponges *Latrunculia* sp²⁶⁻²⁸ and *Prianos melanos* sp²⁹⁻³¹ and suggesting their symbiotic microorganisms origin.

Ascidian alkaloids

The polycyclic aromatic alkaloids exhibiting an array of biological activities and having a pyrido[*k,l*]acridine skeleton are, perhaps, the fastest growing ascidian metabolites³². Ascidiemnin (**13**)³³ and 2-bromoleptoclinidinone (**14**)^{34,35} ex-

hibiting cytotoxic activity towards leukemia cell line in vitro with IC₅₀ of 0.4 µg/ml and ascidiemnin (**13**) also causing the release of calcium

13, R = H

14, R = Br

in the sarcoplasmic reticulum with a potency 7 times greater than caffeine, have been isolated from *Leptoclinides* sp. and *Didemnum* sp. respectively.

Tunicate alkaloids

Nine tetracyclic aromatic alkaloids named cystodytins were isolated from the marine tunicate *Cystodytes dellechiaiei*^{36,37}. Cystodytin A (**15**), B (**16**) and C (**17**) showed both cytotoxic activity

15, R = { }

16, R = { }

17, R = { }

against L 1210 leukemia cells (IC₅₀ 0.2 µg/ml) and powerful calcium-releasing activity in sarcoplasmic reticulum.

The marine ascidian *Lissoclinum vareau*³⁹ furnished the alkaloids varamines A (**18**) and B (**19**) and marine tunicate of the genus *Diplosoma* yielded diplamine (**20**)⁴⁰. Varamines A and B

18, R = Me

19, R = H

and diplamine were all cytotoxic to L 1210 murine leukemia with IC_{50} 0.03, 0.05 and 0.02 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

Thiazinone-containing pentacyclic alkaloids, shermilamines A (**21**)⁴⁰ and B (**22**)⁴¹ exhibiting

cytotoxicity⁴² against KB cells with an IC_{50} of 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, have been isolated from the purple coloured tunicate *Trididemnum* sp. Thiazole-containing polycyclic aromatic alkaloid, kuanoniamines A (**23**), B (**24**) and D (**25**) isolated from an unidentified ascidian showed cytotoxicity against

KB cells⁴³. The ascidian *Amphicarpa meridiana* collected from South Australia yielded an alkaloid, meridine (**26**) which showed cytotoxicity against P₃₈₈ murine leukemia cells at 0.3–0.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ⁴².

Tryptophan-derived alkaloids

The ascidian *Eudistoma olivaceum* has been an extraordinarily rich source of tryptophan-derived

alkaloids⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷. Several alkaloids named eudistomins having a β -carboline system, are obtained from this source. Eudistomin A (**27**) and other eudis-

tomins exhibited significant antiviral activity. Eudistomin C (**28**), E, F, K and L have tetrahydro- β -carboline skeleton with an additional oxathiazepine ring.

Eudistomidins A-F and woodinine, the β -carboline alkaloids were isolated from *Eudistoma glaucers*⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ and *E. frugum*⁵¹, respectively. Eudistomidins B (**30**), C (**31**), and D (**32**) showed cytotoxic activity against murine leukemia L 1210 (IC₅₀ 3.4, 0.36 and 2.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and L 5178 Y (IC₅₀ 3.1, 0.42, and 2.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) cells respectively. Eudistomidins A (**29**) and C (**31**) also exhibited high order of calmodulin antagonistic activity (IC₅₀ = 3×10^{-5} M) while B (**30**) activated actomyosin ATPase in rabbit heart muscle and D (**32**) induced the release of Ca²⁺ from the sarcoplasmic reticulum.

All the β -carboline alkaloids isolated thus far from marine organisms are related biosynthetically, being derived from tryptophan and one other amino acid³².

Grossularines 1 (**33**) and 2 (**34**), the first α -carboline alkaloids, were isolated from the

marine tunicate *Dendrodia grossularia*⁵². Both the alkaloids were selectively active against solid

tumor cells, showing cytotoxicity upto 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against colon and breast tumor cell lines but had ID₅₀ values of only 4 and 7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against L 1210 leukemia cells respectively. It is suggested that probably they act by DNA intercalation⁵³.

Wakayin (**35**), the first pyrroloiminoquinone alkaloid, was isolated from the Fijian ascidian

Clavelina sp.⁵⁴. It exhibited *in vitro* cytotoxicity against the human colon tumor cell line HCT-116 with an IC₅₀ of 0.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. It also inhibited topoisomerase II at 250 μM and gave a 3-fold differential toxicity toward the CHO cell line EM 9 versus BRI, indicating that its cytotoxicity may result from interference with or damage of DNA.

Lysine-derived alkaloids

The tunicate *Clavelina picta*⁵⁵ has been the source of a series indolizine alkaloids named

piclavins. The piclavine (**36-38**) provided by the tunicate differ in the number of double bonds on the side chain and exhibited antifungal and antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacteria, *Candida albicans*, *Geotrichium candidum*, *Aspergillus terreus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Corynebacterium michiganensis*.

Pseudodistomins A (**39**) and B (**40**), the first piperidine alkaloids which differ only in the configuration of a double bond, were isolated

from the Okinawan tunicate *Pseudodistoma kanoko*⁵⁶. The alkaloids **39** and **40** were cytotoxic, having IC₅₀ values of 2.5 and 0.4 µg/ml against the L 1210 and 2.4 and 0.7 µg/ml against the L 5178 Y cell lines respectively. In addition, both the alkaloids exhibited inhibitory activity against calmodulin-activated brain phosphodiesterase with an inhibitory concentration of 3×10^{-5} M.

Tyrosine- and phenylalanine-derived alkaloids

There had been much interest in the caribbean ascidian *Ecteinascidia turbinata* since aqueous extract of the ascidian exhibited both *in vivo* antitumor activity against P₃₈₈ leukemia and powerful immunomodulatory activity⁵⁷. After twenty years several interesting tyrosine derived alkaloids, called ecteinascidins (**41**) have been isolated by two research groups⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. Ecteinascidins exhibited

antitumor activity both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Etzionin (**42**)⁶¹ isolated from an unidentified Red

Sea tunicate, is an unusual alkaloid. It exhibited antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* with a MIC of 3 µg/ml, as well as against *Aspergillus nidulans* and the gram-positive bacterium *Bacillus subtilis*.

Several groups of aromatic pyrrole-containing alkaloids³² have been isolated from tunicates in the last five years. Lukianol A (**43**) and B (**44**), the pyrrolooxazinone alkaloids⁶² have been obtained from an unidentified tunicate from Palmyra Atol. Lukianol A (**43**) exhibited moderate

cytotoxicity against KB cells with a MIC of 1 µg/ml. Rigidin (**45**) a novel pyrrolopyrimidine

alkaloid⁶³ from the Okinawan tunicate *Eudistoma cf rigida*, exhibited calmodulin antagonistic activity

with an IC_{50} value of 5×10^{-5} M for inhibition of calmodulin activated brain phosphodiesterase. Marine ascidian, *Lissoclinum perforatum* has yielded a unique dopamine-derived polysulfide alkaloid, lissoclinotoxin A (**46**)⁶⁴ which exhibited

46

antifungal and antimicrobial activity against a variety of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria with MIC's in the range 0.6–0.1, as well as against pathogenic fungi *Candida albicans* (40 μ g/ml) and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (20 μ g/ml) and cytotoxicity against the human colon cancer HCT-116 cell line with an IC_{90} of 0.05 μ g/ml and also damaged DNA.

Pyridoacridine alkaloids

Amphimedine (**47**) is the first member of the pyridoacridine group of alkaloids, isolated from marine sponge, *Amphimedon* sp.⁶⁵. Since

47

then over 40 alkaloids of this group have been isolated. The pyridoacridines are highly coloured compounds. Currently there is much interest in these alkaloids due to their significant biological properties. Almost all have been reported as having significant cytotoxicity. Several specific biological properties such as anti-HIV activity⁶⁶,

Ca^{2+} release activity⁶⁷, metal chelating property⁶⁸ and intercalation of DNA are exhibited by the members of this group of alkaloids. An excellent review dealing with chemistry and biology of marine pyridoacridine alkaloids has recently appeared⁶⁹.

Pyridoacridine alkaloids have been isolated mainly from sponges and tunicates ornately decorated with bright colours and pattern. These alkaloids are pH indicators. This property is correlated with the presence of at least two basic pyridine like nitrogens and is probably associated with electronic perturbations. Pyridoacridines are typically isolated as refractory microcrystalline solids with reported melting points often above 300°.

Most pyridoacridines show *in vitro* cytotoxicity against cultured tumor cells (L 1210 murine leukemia, P₃₈₈, etc.) or antineoplastic activity in whole animal experiments. The deep-water sponge *Dercitus* sp. yielded the dark violet coloured compound named dercitin (**48**)^{70,71} which inhibited

48

a variety of cultured cell clones at nanomolar concentrations and showed antitumor activity in mice and modest antiviral activity against Herpes

49

simplex and A-59 murine corona virus at micromolar concentration⁷⁰. A detailed study by Burres *et al.*⁷² showed that dercitin (**48**) inhibited both DNA and RNA synthesis by upto 83% at 400 nm. Neoamphimedine (**49**), a regioisomer of amphimedine isolated from the mocronesian sponge. *Xestospongia cf. carbonaria*⁶⁹ was found a potent inhibitor of purified mammalian topoisomerase II (IC₅₀, 1.3 μ M) but not of topoisomerase I.

Pyridoacridine like other marine alkaloids are products of aromatic amino acid metabolism. Kuanoniamine D and shermilamine B (**52**) are produced by the marine tunicate *Cystodytes delechiajei*.

The biosynthesis of shermilamine B (**52**) had been studied with cell-free extracts of the tunicate using 1-[5-3H]tryptophan and [7,8-3H₂] DOPA and feeding of liposomal[2-¹³C]tryptophan to *C. delechiajei* followed by harvesting after 4 months, resulted in ¹³C-labelled shermilamine B. The suggested biosynthetic pathway⁶⁹ of shermilamine B (**52**) is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Over 40 pyridoacridine alkaloids have been isolated till to-date and it is expected that additional structural variations will be added. Pyridoacridine alkaloids do provide good models for synthetic studied. The biological activity of pyridoacridine alkaloids is not only due to intercalation of DNA but other factors are also involved. Since majority of pyridoacridines, come from species in two disparate phyla, sponge and tunicates,

it is likely that symbiotic microorganisms are involved in the production of these alkaloids.

Analogs of bioactive marine alkaloids

Marine invertebrates particularly sponges and tunicates have provided very unusual alkaloids. Since some of these alkaloids are obtained only in very small quantity, it had not been possible to evaluate their biological activities. Efforts should be to make them available synthetically for biological evaluation.

There appears no report on the design, synthesis and biological activities of the compounds using bioactive marine alkaloids as 'Lead compound'. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to make analogs of bioactive marine alkaloids and to evaluate their biological activities.

Aplysinopsin (**53**), an indole derivative, first isolated from the extract of an Australian barrier reef sponge *Thorecta aplysinopsis*, *Fascaplysinopsis reticulata*, caribbean sponge, *Verongia spengelii*⁷³, *Dendrophylla sp*⁷⁴ and mediterranean anthozoan *Astroides calycularis*⁷⁵ and a Japanese coral *Tubastrea aurea*⁷⁶, exhibited inhibitory activity (*in vivo*) against P₃₈₈ in mice (TIC 35% at 0.2 μ g/kg) and cytotoxicity against the cancer cell line P₃₈₈ and L 1210 (ED₅₀, 0.87, 3.8 and 3.7 μ g/ml respectively). It was also found active *in vivo* against B16 (melanoma) assays.

53, R = H
54, R = Me

Methylaplysinopsin (**54**) from *Aplysinopsis reticulata*⁷⁵ showed antidepressant effect in mammals. Further it was found to be a short acting inhibitor of monoamine oxidase, especially with serotonin as substrate. Neurological and neurophysiological evidences indicated that methylaplysinopsin (**54**) potentiates central serotonergic neurotransmission⁷⁷ and had drug potential.

Aplysinopsin (**53**) had been synthesised by condensation of indole-3-carboxaldehyde with 1,3-dimethyl-2-iminoimidazolidin-4-one⁷³. We have achieved a new synthesis of aplysinopsin (**53**). A number of aplysinopsin analogs (**55a-d**) were also synthesised and evaluated for their antimicrobial, antiviral, antileishmanial and CVS activities.

55a, R = Me
55b, R = Et
55c, R = n-Pr.
55d, R = n-But

Tosylation of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (**56a**) (*Method A*, Scheme 2) with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride under phase transfer conditions using

56a, R = H
56b, R = Tosyl
56c, R = Bz
56d, R = Bn

57a, R = Tosyl
57b, R = Bz
57c, R = Bn
57d, R = H

58a, R = Tosyl
58b, R = Bz
58c, R = Bn

59a, R = Tosyl
59b, R = Bz
59c, R = Bn
59d, R = H

Scheme 2

$\text{Bu}_4\text{NH}_4^+\text{HSO}_4^-$ as catalyst afforded *N*-1-*p*-toluenesulphonyl indole-3-carboxaldehyde (**56b**) in 70% yield. Acetic anhydride mediated condensation of **56b** with guanidinoacetic acid gave 3-[(2'-acetamido-5'-acetoxy-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-*p*-toluenesulphonyl-1*H*-indole (**57a**).

in 85% yield. Hydrolysis of **57a** with methanolic ammonia at ambient temperature yielded 3-[(2'-imino-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-*p*-toluenesulphonyl-1*H*-indole (**59a**). Methylation of **59a** with methyl iodide gave 3-[(2'-imino-1',3'-dimethyl-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-*p*-toluene sulphonyl-1*H*-indole (**58a**). Detosylation of **58a** with 10% sodium hydroxide afforded 3-[(2'-imino-1',3'-dimethyl-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1*H*-indole (**53**). The physical and chemical data of **53** were almost identical with aplysinopsin⁷³. Direct comparison of **53** with an authentic sample of aplysinopsin could not be made due to nonavailability of the sample. *Method B*: Treatment of **56a** with benzoyl chloride under phase transfer conditions using $\text{Bu}_4\text{NH}_4^+\text{SO}_4^-$ as catalyst gave *N*-1-benzoylindole-3-carboxaldehyde (**56c**) in 80% yield. Condensation of guanidinoacetic acid with **56c** in presence of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate afforded 3-[(2'-acetamido-5'-acetoxy-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-benzoyl-1*H*-indole (**57b**) in 62% yield. Alkaline hydrolysis of **57b** with methanolic sodium hydroxide at ambient temperature gave 3-[(2'-acetamido-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-benzoyl-1*H*-indole as the minor product (yield 20%) and 3-[(2'-imino-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1*H*-indole (**59d**) in 40% yield. Methylation of **59d** with methyl iodide in the presence of Et_3N gave dimethyl derivative characterised as 3-[(2'-imino-1',3'-dimethyl-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-benzoyl-1*H*-indole (**58b**). Debenzoylation of **58b** with 1*N* sodium hydroxide finally afforded 3-[(2'-imino-1',3'-dimethyl-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1*H*-indole (**53**) identical in all respects with the compound made by method A.

1-Benzylaplysinopsin (**58c**): Benzylation of **56a** with benzyl chloride using $\text{Bu}_4\text{NH}_4^+\text{SO}_4^-$ as phase transfer catalyst gave *N*-1-benzylindole-3-carboxaldehyde (**56d**) in 80% yield. Condensation of **56d** with guanidinoacetic acid in acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate yielded 3-[(2'-acetamido-5'-acetoxy-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-benzyl-1*H*-indole (**58c**) in 37% yield.

Treatment of **58c** with 10% sodium hydroxide at 80° afforded 3-[(2'-imino-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]benzyl-1*H*-indole (**59c**). Methylation of **59c** with methyl iodide finally furnished 3-[(2'-imino-1',3'-dimethyl-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-benzyl-1*H*-indole (**58c**) in 42% yield.

3-[(2'-Imino-1',3'-dialkyl-5'-oxo-4-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1-alkyl-1*H*-indoles (**55a-d**): Condensation of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (**56a**) with guanidine acetic acid in acetic anhydride afforded 3-[(2'-acetamido-5'-acetoxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1*H*-indole (**55d**) in 76% yield. Alkaline hydrolysis of **55d** with sodium hydroxide gave 3-[(2'-imino-5'-oxo-4'-imidazolidinylidene)methylene]-1*H*-indole (**57d**). Alkylation of **57d** in anhydrous DMF separately with methyl iodide, ethyl bromide, *n*-propyl bromide and *n*-butyl bromide in presence of potassium carbonate yielded the corresponding trialkylated derivatives (**55a-d**) respectively.

Aplysinopsin (**53**) and its analogs (**55a-d**, **58a-c** and **57d**) were evaluated for broad biological activities. Of the compounds tested, compounds **55a**, **56b**, **57b** and **57d** showed high order of antileishmanial activity (*in vitro*). Compound **55a** also showed moderate antiviral activity against Ranikhet Disease Virus (RDV) and compounds **56d**, **56c**, **57a**, **57b**, **57c** and **57d** showed moderate antimicrobial activity.

Conclusions :

Although marine organisms have provided a large number of bioactive alkaloids and some with significant biological activity, a drug from this source remains as elusive as it did two decades ago. The chemistry of marine alkaloids with unusual structures has enriched organic chemistry. The role of symbiotic marine microorganism in the production of bioactive marine alkaloids has not been understood in several cases. The use of bioactive marine alkaloids in understanding the biological processes and

elucidation of their biosynthetic pathways are the future areas of research.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. D. S. BHAKUNI and M. SILVA, *Bot. Mar.*, 1974, **17**, 51.
2. D. S. BHAKUNI and M. SILVA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1975, **34**, 36.
3. D. S. BHAKUNI and S. JAIN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1990, **49**, 330.
4. D. S. BHAKUNI, *Indian J. Chem. Sci.*, 1990, **4**, 1.
5. K. AVASTHI and D. S. BHAKUNI, *Indian J. Het. Chem.*, 1993, **2**, 203.
6. H. CHR and KREBS CHR, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1986, **49**, 157.
7. D. J. FAULKNER, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1986, **3**, 1; 1987, **4**, 539; 1988, **5**, 613; 1990, **7**, 269; 1991, **8**, 97; 1992, **9**, 323.
8. P. R. BURKHOLDER, R. M. PFISTER and F. P. LEITZ, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1966, **14**, 649.
9. F. M. LOVELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 4510.
10. H. LAATSH and H. PUDLEINER, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1989, **9**, 863.
11. R. J. ANDERSEN, M. S. WOLFE R. J. ANDERSON and D. J. FAULKNER, *J. Mar. Biol.*, 1974, **24**, 281.
12. S. J. WRATTEN, M. S. WOLFE, R. J. ANDERSON and D. J. FAULKNER, *J. Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1977, **11**, 411.
13. A. TAKAHASHI, S. KUROSAWA, D. IKEDA, Y. OKAMI and T. U. TAKEUCHI, *J. Antibiot.*, 1989, **42**, 1556.
14. A. TAKAHASHI, D. IKEDA, H. NAKAMURA, S. SULASAWA, Y. OKAMI, T. TAKEUCHI and Y. LITAKA, *J. Antibiot.*, 1989, **42**, 1562.
15. W. FENICAL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 1673.
16. T. KOSUGE, K. TSUJI and K. HIRAI, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1982, **3255**.
17. T. KOSUGE, K. TSUJI, K. HIRAI and T. FUKUYAMA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1985, **33**, 3051.
18. T. YASUMOTO, D. YASUMURA, M. YOTSU, T. MICHISHITA, A. ENDO and Y. KOTAKI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1986, **50**, 739.
19. M. YOTSU, T. YAMAZAKI, Y. MEGURO, A. ENDO, M. MURATA, H. NAOKI and T. YASUMOTO, *Toxicol.*, 1987, **25**, 225.
20. T. NOGUCHI, J. TEON, O. ARAKAWA, H. SUGITA, Y.

- DEGUCHI, Y. SHIDA and K. HASHIMOTO, *J. Biochem.*, 1986, **99**, 311.
21. M. KODAMA, T. OGATA, S. SATO and S. SAKAMOTA, *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*, 1990, **61**, 203.
 22. A. NUMATA, C. TAKAHASHI, T. MATSUSHITA, K. KAWAI, Y. USAMI, E. MATSUMURA, M. INOUE, H. OHISHI and T. SHINGUE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **33**, 1621.
 23. J. KOBAYASHI and M. ISHIBASHI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 1753.
 24. B. R. COPP, C. M. IRELAND and L. R. BARROWS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 4596.
 25. D. S. BHAKUNI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1993, **53**, 430.
 26. N. B. PERRY, J. W. BLUNT, J. D. MCCOMBS and M. H. G. MUNRO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 5476.
 27. N. B. PERRY, J. W. BLUNT, J. D. MCCOMB and M. H. G. MUNRO, *Tetrahedron*, 1988, **53**, 1727.
 28. N. B. PERRY, J. W. BLUNT, M. H. G. MUNRO, T. HIGA and SAKAI R., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 4127.
 29. J. KOBAYASHI, J. F. CHENG, M. ISHIBASHI, H. NAKAMURA, Y. OHIZUMI, Y. HIRATA, T. SASAKI, H. LU and J. CLARDY *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28** 4939.
 30. J.-F. CHENG, Y. OHIZUMI, M. R. WALCHLI, H. NAKAMURA, Y. HIRATA, T. SASAKI and J. KOBAYASHI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 4621.
 31. J. M. FRINCKE and D. J. FAULKNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 265.
 32. B. S. DAVIDSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 1771.
 33. J. KOBAYASHI, J. CHENG, M. R. WALCHLI, NAKAMURA, H. YOSHIMASA, S. TAKUMA and Y. OHIZUMI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 1800.
 34. S. BLOOR and F. J. SCHMITZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 6134.
 35. F. S. DE GUZMAN and F. J. SCHMITZ, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 1069.
 36. J. KOBAYASHI, J. CHENG, M. R. MALCHLI, H. NAKAMURA, H. YOSHIMASA, S. TAKUMA and Y. OHIZUMI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 1800.
 37. J. KOBAYASHI, M. TSUDA, A. TANABE, M. ISHIBASHI, J. CHENG, S. YAMAMURA and T. SASAKI, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1991, **54**, 1634.
 38. T. MOLINSKI and C. M. IRELAND, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 4256.
 39. G. A. CHARYULU, T. C. MCKEL and C. M. IRELAND, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 4201.
 40. N. M. COORAY, P. J. SCHEUER, L. PARKANYI and J. CLARDY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **63**, 4619.
 41. A. R. CARROL, N. M. COORAY, A. POINER and P. J. SCHEUER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 4232.
 42. F. J. SCHMITZ, F. S. DE GUZMAN, M. B. HOSSAIN and D. VAN DER HELM, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 804.
 43. A. R. CARROLL and P. J. SCHEUER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 4426.
 44. K. L. RINEHART, JR., J. KOBAYASHI, G. C. HARBOUR, R. G. HUGHES, JR., S. A. MIZSAK and T. A. SCOHILL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 1524.
 45. J. KOBAYASHI, G. C. HARBOUR, J. GILMORE and K. L. RINEHART, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 1526.
 46. K. L. RINEHART, JR., J. KOBAYASHI, G. C. HARBOUR, J. GILMORE, M. MASCAL, T. G. HOLT, L. S. SHIELD and F. LAFARGUE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 3378.
 47. K. F. KINZER and J. H. CARDELLINA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28**, 925.
 48. J. KOBAYASHI, H. NAKAMURA, Y. OHIZUMI and Y. HIRATA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 1191.
 49. J. KOBAYASHI, J. CHENG, T. OHTA, S. NOZOE, Y. OHIZUMI and T. SASAKI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 3666.
 50. O. MURATA, H. SHIGEMORI, M. ISHIBASHI, K. SUGAMA, K. HAYASHI and J. KOBAYASHI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 3539.
 51. C. DEBITUS, D. LAURENT and M. PAIS, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1988, **51**, 799.
 52. C. MOQUIN-PATTEY and M. GUYOT, *Tetrahedron*, 1989, **45**, 3445.
 53. N. HELBECQUE, J. L. BERVIER, J. P. HENICARD, C. MOQUIN and M. GUYOT, *Biochem. Biophys.*, 1987, **9**, 271.
 54. B. R. COPP, C. M. IRELAND and L. R. BARROWS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 4596.
 55. M. F. RAUB, J. H. CARDELLINA and T. F. SPANDE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 2257.
 56. M. ISHIBASHI, Y. OHIZUMI, T. SASAKI, H. NAKAMURA, Y. HIRATA and J. KOBAYASHI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 450.
 57. M. M. SIGEL, L. L. WELLHAM, W. LICHTER, L. E. DUDECK, J. L. GARGUS and A. H. LUCAS, *Food-Drug Sea Proc.*, 1970, 1969, 2821.
 58. A. E. WRIGHT, D. A. FORLEO, G. P. GUNAWARDANA, S. SUNASEKERA, F. E. KOEHN and O. MCCONNELL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 4508.
 59. K. L. RINEHART JR., T. G. HOLT, N. L. FREGLAN, J. G. STROH, P. A. KEIFER, F. SUN, L. H. LI and D. G. MARTIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 4512.
 60. K. L. RINEHART, JR., T. G. HOLT, N. L. FREGEAN, J. G. STROH, P. A. KEIFER, F. SUN, H. LI and D. G. MARTIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 1676.
 61. S. HIRSCH, A. MIROZ, P. MCCARTHY and Y. KASHMAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 4291.
 62. W. Y. YOSHIDA, K. K. LEE, A. R. CARROL and P. J. SCHEUER, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1992, **75**, 1721.

63. J. KOBAYASHI, J. -F. CHENG, Y. KIKUCHI, M. ISHIBASHI, S. YAMAMURA, Y. OHIZUMI, T. OHTA and S. NOZOE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 4613.
64. M. LITAUDON and M. GUYOT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 911.
65. F. J. SCHMITZ, S. K. AGARWAL, S. P. GUNASEKERA, P. G. SCHMIDT and J. N. SHOOLERY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 4835.
66. I. B. TARAPOREWALA, J. W. CESSAC, T. C. CHANH, A. W. DELGADO and R. F. SCHINAZI, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, **35**, 2744.
67. J. KOBAYASHI, J. CHENG, M. R. WALCHLI, H. NAKAMURA, Y. HIRATA, T. SASAK and Y. OHIZUMI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 1800.
68. G. P. GUNAWARDANA, F. E. KEEHN, A. Y. LEE, J. CHARDY, H. Y. HE and D. J. FAULKNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **57**, 1528.
69. T. F. MOLINSKI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 1825.
70. G. P. GUNAWARDANA, S. KOHMOTO, S. P. GUNASEKERA, O. J. MCCONNELL and F. E. KOEHN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 4356.
71. G. P. GUNAWARDANA, F. E. KOEHN, A. Y. LEE, J. CLARDY, H. Y. HE and D. J. FAULKNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **57**, 1523.
72. N. S. BURREN, S. SAZESH, G. P. GUNAWARDANA and J. CLEMENT, *J. Cancer Res.*, 1989, **49**, 5267.
73. R. H. HOLLENBEAK and F. J. SCHARIT, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1977, **40**, 479.
74. G. GUELLA, I. MACINI, H. ZIBROWISS and F. PICTRA, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **79**, 1444.
75. E. FATTRUSSO, V. LANZOLTI, S. MAGNO and E. NOVELLINE, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1985, **48**, 924.
76. N. FUSETANI, M. ASANO, S. MATSUNAGA and K. HASHIMOTO, *Comp. Biochem. Physical. (B)*, 1986, **85**, 845.
77. K. M. BOURA and R. I. GALLO, *Heterocycles*, 1990, **31**, 447.